

Midas

MARGINAL LANDS, INDUSTRIAL CROPS
AND INNOVATIVE BIO-BASED VALUE CHAINS

Deliverable D5.1

Mapping potential biomass-to-product(s) pathways

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101082070.

Document summary

Deliverable number	5.1
Title	Mapping potential biomass-to-product(s) pathways
Version	1
Work package n°	5
Lead Beneficiary	UHOH
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Submission date	31.10.2023
Dissemination Level	Public
Project acronym and title	MIDAS
Grant Agreement n°	101082070
Project coordinator	Efi Alexopoulou (CRES)
Reviewer	Name and affiliation
Review date	

Statement of Originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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Executive summary

A sustainable bioeconomy can be achieved by replacing non-renewable resources by using locally available biomass and changing production patterns while closing material cycles (Dietz et al. 2018). A promising perspective on this bioeconomy transformation takes advantage of industrial crops grown on marginal lands to produce high-value-added bio-based products (Cossel et al. 2019). The idea behind this sustainable feedstock production on marginal lands is that shifting bio-based production systems to these areas can address sustainability issues in a spatial context, including competition with food production and direct and indirect land-use change problems (Muscat et al. 2022). This approach has the potential to strengthen the growing bio-based industry, reduce competition in land use, increase farmer incomes, and increase the value of marginal land (Elbersen et al. 2017).

The EU Horizon 2020 project MIDAS (Grant agreement ID: 101082070) was established with the ambition of building innovative regional adapted value chains and webs to support a sustainable bioeconomy. In MIDAS different promising industrial crops are grown in innovative cropping systems with annual and perennial crops (intercropping, agroforestry) on marginal land (WP2; WP3). These crops can support the bio-based industry by providing low-ILUC feedstock for numerous bio-based applications (WP4). WP5 aims to design sustainable value chains and webs with the biomass, stemming from farming systems tested in different case studies (WP3). The MIDAS project goes beyond the farm scale and considers the entire value chain in site-adapted biomass-to-product pathways.

This report “Mapping potential biomass-to-product(s) pathways” (Deliverable 5.1) represents the results of task 5.1 as summarized in the Grant Agreement GA no. 101082070. Data for this report were primarily derived through stakeholder consultation via data templates developed for this purpose and interviews with research partners in WP3 and industry partners in WP4. Also, literature sources were used to fill data gaps.

A simplified structure of a bio-based value chain entails biomass production and supply, conversion processes and final use. The same applies to biomass-to-product(s) pathways which are site-specific combinations of a particular type of biomass, the biomass treatment and conversion processes and one or more products by it. The process of developing innovative bio-based value chains and webs starts by describing the biomass production in innovative cropping systems on marginal land (WP3) and their use for innovative bio-based products (WP4).

In the MIDAS project a number of promising industrial crops have been selected to be tested in several case studies with different marginality conditions in Europe under real operational conditions (farm-scale) in different cropping systems like agroforestry and intercropping (WP3). These case studies are aimed at, inter alia, collecting real productivity data to be used for value-chain analysis and integrated assessment in WP5. Nineteen case studies were developed in nine different countries by thirteen partners (CIEMAT, CREA, CRES, CZECHEMP, European Carbon Farmers, GuaTecs, IFVC, ITAB, Novamont, Soltub, UHOH, UNIBO and UNICT). These case studies were established as large field trials using different industrial crops (detailed descriptions in chapter 5).

The different types of biodiversity-friendly and climate resilient low ILUC feedstocks produced during the case studies will be transformed through various processing routes into twelve different products (WP4). Lignocellulosic crops with their special characteristics (e.g, high fiber content and quality) are directly tested for the manufacture of biomaterials (Task 4.2). Compounds of interest are extracted from oilcrops and speciality crops (Task 4.1) before the bagasse resulting from the process is used following the concept of the circular use of biomass (Task 4.2) (detailed descriptions in chapter 6).

For this deliverable we use a superstructure approach to map all biomass-to-product pathways resulting from the industrial crops grown on marginal land. A superstructure is a flow-sheet that shows all the process alternatives for a given feedstock (Kim et al. 2013).

We started by identifying potential pathways for every crop using a literature search. Then, a preliminary biomass-to-product pathway structure was developed and sent to the MIDAS partner in WP3 and WP4. The partners reviewed these pathways and adjusted them based on their knowledge using a data entry sheet. Follow-up discussions among partners from WP3, WP4, and WP5 helped to further refine the identified pathways.

Bringing together different regions, marginalities and stakeholders, we identified **129 potential biomass-to-product pathways** from **18 different non-edible industrial crops** and **12 innovative products** that are under investigation in the MIDAS project. All biomass-to-product pathways have been identified with the support from different MIDAS partners (WP3; WP4)

The resulting biomass-to-product(s) pathways were integrated into feedstock-category specific superstructures (Figure 1). Adapting the superstructure approach to the context of MIDAS allows us to show the **technological potential** for every industrial crop tested in MIDAS.

Figure 1 Superstructure approach for the mapping of biomass-to-product pathways (Authors)

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1. Introduction

A growing bioeconomy demands an adequate supply of sustainably grown biomass to support the development of innovative bioproducts and applications (Lewandowski 2015). The diversification of biomass resources is key for a bioeconomy to prevent challenges related to food security and indirect land-use change.

However, an increasing biomass production carries a multitude of social-ecological risks, such as an increased use of fertilizers and pesticides, negative impacts from land-use changes and additional pressure on water resources (Fernando et al. 2015; Cossel et al. 2019). The EU Horizon 2020 project MIDAS (Grant agreement ID: 101082070.) was established with the ambition of building on the development of innovative value chains by growing selected non-edible (industrial) crops on marginal lands to produce low-ILUC feedstock for bio-based applications following the biorefinery concept (circular biomass use).

To achieve this the MIDAS project aims:

- to understand and map the actual marginal lands in Europe (now, in 2030 & 2050) for low ILUC feedstock production (WP1).
- to optimize selected industrial crops adapted to marginal lands through modern biotechnology tools and tailored agronomic practices towards low ILUC cropping systems (WP2; WP3).
- to develop case studies of low-ILUC cropping systems (intercropping & agroforestry) on marginal agricultural land on farm level for present and future farming systems (WP3).
- to develop innovative bio-based products (namely biochemical, composites, and elastomers) following a bio refinery concept and the circular use of biomass (WP4).
- to design innovative resource efficient bio-based value chains and webs and to perform integrated sustainability assessment, including impacts on biodiversity (field & landscape level) (WP5).
- to develop business plans to foster circularity at farm level by engaging the farming community, industrial actors and academia through the projects' Case Studies (WP6)

In MIDAS different promising industrial crops are grown in innovative cropping systems (intercropping, agroforestry) with annual and perennial crops on marginal land (WP2; WP3).

Marginal land: "Lands having limitations which in aggregate are severe for sustained application of a given use and/or are sensitive to land degradation, as a result of inappropriate human intervention, and/or have lost already part or all of their productive capacity as a result of inappropriate human intervention and also include contaminated and potentially contaminated sites that form a potential risk to humans, water, ecosystems, or other receptors" (Elbersen et al. 2017)).

These crops can cope well with water scarcity/stress and they have been proven to be effective to reducing soil erosion. They can support the bio-based industry by providing low-ILUC feedstock for numerous bio-based applications (biochemical, biomaterials, elastomers) including bioenergy while optimizing the circular biomass use (WP4).

Producing biomass is the initial step of the value generation process in a bioeconomy. Many other stakeholders are involved in using and valorizing bio-based resources. Complicated relationships exist between those providing biomass (primary producers) and those using biomass (intermediate producers and consumers). The idea of a value chain, pioneered by Michael Porter in the 1980s, helps to conceptualize the interdependencies between actors, processes, and products from cultivation to consumption.

The value chain approach of WP5 is demonstrated by designing sustainable value chains with the biomass, stemming from farming systems tested in different case studies (WP3) as starting point and the modelling of all potential biomass processing steps that deliver the innovative bio-based products (WP4). The development of innovative value chains requires the selection of suitable biomass-to-product(s) pathways.

Biomass-to-product(s) pathways are site-specific combinations of a particular type of biomass, the biomass treatment and conversion processes and one or more products by it.

A simplified structure of a bio-based value chains entails biomass production and supply, conversion processes and final use. Related activities such as biomass pretreatment, storage, transportation, packaging and commercialization are also components of bio-based value chains (Zörb et al. 2018; Lewandowski 2015)

Bio-based value chains are the full range of activities and the sequence of processes and stakeholders involved from biomass production to the conversion through different technologies into material and energetic products (Kaplinsky and Morris 2001; Lewandowski 2015; Zörb et al. 2018).

As shown in Figure 2 value chains and biomass-to-product pathways can be represented through linear flow diagrams that show the processes that inputs undergo until their life end (Zörb et al. 2018).

Figure 2 Simplified value chain structure (Authors)

Primary production, in the case of MIDAS the case studies in WP3, provide different type of feedstock from oil crops, lignocellulosic crops and speciality crops. Further pretreatment and transformation of biomass are performed through the different combinations of physical, chemical, thermochemical and biotechnological processes (WP4). Subsequently, manifold bio-based products are obtained (WP4), providing for example biolubricants and wood-based materials.

In order to assure a sustainable supply of bio-based resources and products, all phases in the manufacturing process, from biomass supply through to final products, must comply to the key sustainability criteria. In order to accomplish this, complete value chains must be considered.

In WP5 activities are structured around five Tasks: The identification and screening of all potential biomass-to-product(s) pathways by combining the selected industrial crops (WPs 2 & 3) produced in innovative regional cropping systems in regional case studies (WP3) and the bio-based products that are developed in WP4 (Task 5.1). Then, these identified biomass-to-product(s) pathways will be assessed (Task 5.2) to estimate their suitability and potential contribution to sustainable rural development applying a multi-criteria framework to identify the most promising combinations. Furthermore, for these most promising biomass-to-product(s) pathways Life-cycle-sustainability assessments (LCSA) will be carried out including their biodiversity impact and restoration potentials (Task 5.3; Task 5.4). Finally, sustainable bio-based value webs will be designed applying all information generated and recommendations for their implementation will be developed (Task.5.5).

This deliverable presents the results of Task 5.1, i.e. the mapping of biomass-to-product pathways.

Chapter 2 describes the methodological approach and the data collection procedure. Chapter 3,4 and 5 highlight agricultural aspects including the marginal land concept, description of industrial crops in MIDAS and the case studies in innovative cropping systems (WP3). Chapter 6 shows the feedstock conversion technologies and resulting bio-based products (WP4). The remainder of the deliverable, chapter 7, presents the resulting biomass-to-product pathways in superstructures.

2. Methodological approach and data collection

Mapping of biomass-to-product pathways

To shape the process towards biobased value chains and webs we started by looking at the regional case studies in WP3 and the innovative biobased products in WP4. As shown in figure 3, for every case study on industrial crops grown on marginal land in innovative cropping systems we identified the region, climate, marginality, cropping system and industrial crops (1). Additionally, we identified the type of use and current application for every industrial crop tested in these case studies.

For the innovative biobased products (WP4) we described the processing steps, feedstock conversion technology and identified the feedstock requirements (2).

Following that, we conducted a literature review to initially match the feedstock production (WP3) with the conversion technology and bio-based products (WP4). This resulted in preliminary biomass-to-product pathways (3). These preliminary pathways were sent to partners from WP3 and WP4 for review. The partners were asked to adjust and add (if necessary) to the preliminary identified biomass-to-product pathways for MIDAS (4).

Figure 3 Methodological approach for the mapping of biomass-to-product pathways (Authors)

The resulting biomass-to-product pathways were then integrated into superstructure(s).

Superstructure approach

The superstructure is a flowsheet that shows all the process alternatives for a given feedstock. This approach is widely used for biorefinery design and analysis (Elyasi et al. 2021; Gu et al. 2022; Del Álvarez Castillo-Romo et al. 2018; Kim et al. 2013; Ng et al. 2018).

Superstructure: Network that contains alternative biomass-to-product pathways, starting from the feedstocks, including processes, platforms and ending in products (Kim et al. 2013)

Adapting this approach to the context of MIDAS allows us to show the **technological potential** for every industrial crop tested in MIDAS.

Figure 4 Superstructure approach for the mapping of biomass-to-product pathways (Authors)

For this Deliverable we therefore build (technology) superstructure(s) that consists of a wide range of feedstocks (industrial crops) along with the corresponding conversion technology, intermediates and final products (Fig. 4).

In this superstructure(s), details of the crop category and feedstock, the process and intermediates, as well as the resulting products can be shown.

Figure 5 Colour code for the presentation of biomass-to-product pathways (superstructure)

Figure 5 shows the colour code that has been used to graphically represent the biomass-to-product pathways in a superstructure approach. The crop category is presented in light blue, the feedstock (industrial crop) in turquoise, conversion processes in green, intermediates in grey and the end-products in red.

Data collection and tailored data templates

Data for this Deliverable as well as Deliverable 5.2 were primarily derived through stakeholder consultation via data templates and interviews with research partners in WP3 and industry partners in WP4. Also, literature sources were used to fill data gaps.

In this initial step towards regional bio-based value chains and webs separate data entry sheets for the innovative cropping systems in WP3 and the bio-based products in WP4 were developed. The spreadsheets have been developed using Microsoft Office Excel.

The Excel spreadsheets prepared are a user-friendly tool, that MIDAS partners could easily fill out providing the necessary information. Both templates have a similar structure, currently consisting of five (WP3) and six (WP4) sections (see Table 1 & 2)

Table 1 Structure of the data entry sheet for WP3 (innovative cropping systems/case studies)

Section 1 WP3:	Basic information about the case study - regional information (climate, marginality, soil characteristic, land use), case study design (size, crops, cycle), information about cultivation (propagation, fertilization, harvesting, etc.)
Section 2 WP3	Pathway assessment - Criteria with respective questions and scoring logic
Section 3 WP3	Biomass-to product pathways – all potential biomass-to-product pathways from the respective crops of the case study
Section 4 WP3	Place to add interesting publications
Section 5 WP3	Place to add pictures

Table 2 Structure of the data entry sheet for WP4 (innovative bio-based products)

Section 1 WP4	Basic information about the bio-based products – feedstock (conversion route, suitable crops, logistics), processing (pre-treatment, scale, amount, by-products, TRL), product (composition, lifetime), market information
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Section 2 WP4	Process design information (AUA) - process diagramm, process flow description, process conditions, process efficiency
Section 3 WP4	Pathway assessment - Criteria with respective questions and scoring logic
Section 4 WP4	Biomass-to product pathways – all potential biomass-to-product pathways related to the bio-based product
Section 5 WP4	Place to add interesting publications
Section 6 WP4	Place to add pictures

The information gathered through these data entry sheets are presented throughout this Deliverable as well as Deliverable 5.2. The same data as well as the collection sheets will, at a later stage of the project serve as a starting point and tool for subsequent tasks in WP5.

3. Description of marginal land

The pursuit of a growing bioeconomy requires an adequate supply of sustainably produced biomass. To sustainably meet this demand, novel bio-based production systems that provide both biomass and multiple ecosystem services need to be identified and developed. The MIDAS project has been established with the ambition to further develop low - ILUC crop production systems on marginal lands (WP2; WP3).

Elbersen et al. 2017 define marginal land as “Lands having limitations which in aggregate are severe for sustained application of a given use and/or are sensitive to land degradation, as a result of inappropriate human intervention, and/or have lost already part or all of their productive capacity as a result of inappropriate human intervention and also include contaminated and potentially contaminated sites that form a potential risk to humans, water, ecosystems, or other receptors”.

Table 3 highlights the marginality classification developed in the MAGIC project which is used to classify the case studies in MIDAS.

Table 3 Overview of the natural constraints (marginality) as classified within the MAGIC project - taken from (Cossel et al. 2019)

Constraint category	Factor category	Thresholds/specifications
Category 1: “Natural constraint based marginality”	Low temperature (insufficient thermal time)	Length of growing period ≤ 180 days Thermal time sum ≤ 1500 degree days
	Dryness – Too dry conditions	Precipitation / Potential Evapotranspiration (P/ET ≤ 0.5)
	Limited soil drainage and excess soil moisture	Wet 80 cm > 6 months
		Wet 40 cm > 11 months
		Poorly or very poorly drained Gleyic colour pattern within 40 cm
Unfavorable soil texture and stoniness	Soil moisture above field capacity for >230 days (excessive soil moisture) Topsoil with stones (15% of topsoil volume is coarse material, rock outcrop, boulder) Texture class in half of the soil in a profile of 100 cm vertical depth is sand, loamy sand	

Constraint category	Factor category	Thresholds/specifications
	Shallow rooting depth	Organic soil, defined as having 'organic matter $\geq 30\%$ of at least 40 cm Topsoil with 30% or more clay and presence of vertical properties within 100 cm The physical anchorage of the rooting system (rooting depth ≤ 30 cm) The provision/storage of nutrients and water The possibility of mechanized tillage
	Poor chemical properties (Soil salinity, soil sodicity, soil acidity)	The possibility of mechanized tillage Limitation to plant growth due to toxic elements in soil Vulnerability to waterlogging Damage to soil structure (and consequently increase in risk of erosion) Limited availability of nutrients for plants Salinity ≥ 4 dS/m in topsoil Sodicity ≥ 6 ESP in half or more of the 100-cm surface layer Soil Acidity of topsoil with pH (H ₂ O) ≤ 5
	Steep slope	Slope $\geq 15\%$
Category 2: "Socio-economic-political constraints"		Lack of awareness (alternative strategies – lack of know-how etc.) Social norms (adoption of same cropping patterns as done by elders) Economic viability, especially of set-aside, small land holdings Lack of infrastructure Lack of policies Lack of governmental programs such as extension services
Category 3: "Endangered Sites"		Lands which are currently productive but will be transformed into marginal lands in the long term if not managed properly (also, lack of know-how or lack of awareness from farmers/government).

The introduction of low-input systems on these marginal lands can enable farmers to grow industrial crops on these lands, taking into account socio-economic and environmental aspects (Cossel et al. 2019). The implementation of these low-input systems depends primarily on the management system and requires a site-specific perspective to cope with different challenges that might arise (Figure 6) (Cossel et al. 2019; Fernando et al. 2018).

Figure 6 Overview of environmental challenges regarding marginal land (MAL) management taken from (Burland und Cossel 2023) based on (Confalonieri et al. 2014)

Utilizing marginal agricultural land low-input systems for the cultivation of industrial crops can promote a sustainable bioeconomy development by producing resources-efficient crops for industrial uses (Csikós und Tóth 2023).

4. Industrial crops in MIDAS

Industrial crops are defined as crops that are grown to produce resources useful to industrial processes. The development of “marginal agricultural land low-input systems” (MALLIS) always begins with the selection of the most promising industrial crop, because all other agricultural practices (tillage, fertilization, weeding, irrigation, etc.) strongly depend on the type and site-specific performance of the crop (Cossel et al. 2019). In MIDAS 17 industrial crops were chosen as promising by the crop experts and are investigated in different innovative cropping systems. They can be divided into three categories: oil crops, lignocellulosic crops, and speciality/multipurpose crops. An overview of the selected crops is given in Table 4.

Table 4 Industrial crops investigated in the MIDAS project

Oil crops	Lignocellulosic crops	Speciality crops
Crambe	Hemp	Cocksfoot
Cardoon	Sorghum	Melilotus
Castor	Miscanthus	Guayule
Safflower	Poplar; <i>Black poplar</i>	Lavender
Carinata	Siberian Elm	
	Switchgrass	
	White Mustard	

Each of the industrial crops listed in Table 4 can supply feedstock for a multitude of bio-based products, promoting the bioeconomy and providing farmers with diversification alternatives (Scordia et al. 2022). Additionally, they provide smart sustainable cropping options that can facilitate income diversification (Panoutsou und Chiaramonti 2020).

In MIDAS industrial crops are classified under three categories: lignocellulosic, oil and specialty crops. Lignocellulosic crops are mainly formed by polymers of cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin. Oil crops are all plants which produce vegetable oils. Finally, specialty crops are grown for special components used for example in pharmaceuticals, medicines and novel products.

To characterize every industrial crop in MIDAS previous project results from the MAGIC project (MAGIC 2023) were taken, updated and extended based on literature as well as discussions with project partners. The results are shown in Table 5:

Table 5 Description of MIDAS crops

Common name	Latin name	Life Cycle	Type of use	Current use	Potential innovative application in MIDAS	Crop description
Crambe	<i>Crambe abyssinica Hochst x R.E. Fries</i>	Annual	Oil	Erucamide (slip agent in plastics); high temperature resistant industrial lubricant; chemicals (erucyl alcohol, behenic acid, behenic alcohol); seed-meal, ad mixture up to 5% in cattle feed	Biodegradable biolubrificants, Agricultural Biostimulants, Biodegradable in soil mulch films; seed meal: adhesives for particleboards	Annual industrial oilcrop, origin in the Mediterranean and in highlands of east Africa, well adapted to the cool and wet climate conditions of large parts of Europe. Belongs to the Brassicaceae. Plant height ~116-183 cm (average 120); root depth ~15cm; total above round biomass 400 -600 g m ⁻² ; needs spring rainfall.
Cardoon	<i>Cynara cardunculus L.</i>	Perennial (C3)	Oil, Lignocelulose	Traditional Food, Forage, CHP, erosion mitigation, wildlife habitat	Biodegradable biolubrificants, Agricultural Biostimulants, Biodegradable in soil mulch films, Bioherbicides; seed meal: adhesives for particleboards	Cardoon is a perennial, dicot, herbaceous, lignocellulosic (C3) plant belonging to the Compositae (Asteraceae) family, closely related to globe artichoke (<i>C. cardunculus var. scolymus</i> (L.)), native to Mediterranean environments. It has been traditionally cultivated as vegetable in Mediterranean regions for century to produce edible stalks. For bioenergy purpose, it is a good candidate to be grown in the dry lands of the Mediterranean region as lignocellulosic and oilseed crop. The seeds are rich in oil and could be mechanically harvested separately from the rest of the biomass
Castor	<i>Ricinus communis L.</i>	Annual	Oil	Oil has different applications in the oleochemistry, in particular polymer production for textile and plastic material	Biodegradable biolubrificants, Agricultural Biostimulants, Biodegradable in soil mulch films; seed meal: adhesives for particleboards	Oilseed species belonging to the Euphorbiaceae family. It's a summer annual species which can grow also a perennial in tropical climate. Plants can grow up to 3 m tall, but dwarf hybrids are now available on the market to allow mechanical harvest. Seeds are characterized by oil content >50%, but the toxic compound ricin is also present. Studies conducted in several Mediterranean nations to evaluate different castor cultivars revealed a seed production potential of up to 4 Mg ha ⁻¹ (Pari et al. 2022).
Safflower	<i>Carthamus dictorius L.</i>	Annual	Oil	Food and feed application	Biodegradable biolubrificants, Agricultural Biostimulants, Biodegradable in soil mulch films, Bioherbicides; seed meal: adhesives for particleboards	Highly branched, herbaceous, thistle-like annual plant. Plants can be up to 2 m tall. Differently from sunflower, safflower is able to withstand low temperature, and winter types are available It is commercially cultivated for vegetable oil extracted from the seeds but also as a source of orange-yellow pigments. High oleic hybrids are also available in the market as for sunflower
Carinata	<i>Brassica carinata A. Braun</i>	Annual	Oil	Food, Biofuel	Biodegradable biolubrificants, Agricultural	Belonging to the Brassicaceae family, carinata is a low input crop, very tolerant to different biotic and abiotic stresses, and also to seed shattering. Plants are highly vigorous and they can present

					Biostimulants, Biodegradable in soil mulch films; seed meal: adhesives for particleboards	both white and yellow flowers. Despite being a spring crop in mild environments it could be grown also as a winter crop
Hemp	<i>Cannabis sativa L.</i> (<i>Crotalaria juncea L.</i>)	Annual (C3)	Fiber, Oil	Food, textiles, ropes, composites materials, insulation mats, car interior panels, reinforced expanded starch foams in the food packaging sector, hemp concret	Particleboards, Graphene & Nanocarbons, Biochar	Hemp is an annual, dicotyledonous, warm - season (C3) plant belonging to the Cannabaceae family, adapted to a wide range of environments. Naturally it is dioecious, with the male plants that are taller and that come to flower earlier than the female ones. It is wind pollinated and the male plants die after producing millions of pollen grains. Monoecious varieties have been selected in modern times to reduce some agronomic problems such as an efficient mechanization for harvesting the seeds, and the lower fibre quality and yield losses encountered when harvesting dioecious varieties at seed maturity
Sorghum	<i>Sorghum bicolor (L.) Moench</i>	Annual (C4)	Lignocelulose	Seeds are used for feed and food application, the entire biomass or the residual biomass is used for biogas production	Particleboards, Graphene & Nanocarbons, Biochar	It's a C4 grass species largely grown in warm climate worldwide. Different types exist with different end-uses covering: food and non-food application. Plant morphology is depending to the end-uses, sugar and biomass types can be as tall as 4 m. Sorghum is characterized by high water use efficiency compared to corn
Miscanthus	<i>Miscanthus x giganteus</i>	Perennial (C4)	Lignocelulose	Solid fuel; Building material (Isolation, thatching, panels), animal bedding, biocomposites	Particleboards, Graphene & Nanocarbons, Biochar	Perennial rhizomatous grass native to East Asia. High biomass yield potential due to C4 photosynthetic mechanism. Miscanthus x giganteus is presently the only commercially grown miscanthus genotype. It is a triploid, sterile hybrid between Miscanthus sinensis and Miscanthus sacchariflorus. Miscanthus is exceptionally energy efficient, and may grow to a height of 3-3.5 metres. Additionally, it requires little nourishment and uses nitrogen effectively, so that it could thrive on MAL with very modest amounts of fertiliser input (Panoutsou und Chiaramonti 2020). A range of 2 to 44 t ha ⁻¹ have been reported as harvestable Miscanthus yields (dry matter) globally, with yields of 27 to 44 t ha ⁻¹ in Europe.
Cocksfoot	<i>Dactylis</i>	Annual	Lignocelulose	Animal feed, Bioenergy, paper production	Biochar, MDF Boards	Dactylis is a genus of Eurasian and North African plants in the bluegrass subfamily within the grass family. Dactylis is native to North Africa, they are found throughout the world, and are an invasive species.
Poplar	<i>Populus spp.</i>	Perennial	Lignocelulose, wood chips	Bioenergy, solid biofuel, fire wood, pellets, boards, plywood for ve-	MDF Boards, Graphene & Nanocarbons, Biochar	Any tree of the salicaceous genus Populus, of N temperate regions, having triangular leaves, flowers borne in catkins, and light soft wood. It's a fast -growing plant which adapt well to biofuel production as short rotation coppice. Poplar is very vigorous and it can

Black poplar	<i>Populus nigra</i>	Perennial	Lignocelulose	randa, wood for furniture, building material. Wildlife (birds) habitat		grow up to 40-m tall in moisture rich soils. It is estimated that poplar yields range from 7 to 10 Mg ha ⁻¹ dry mass on average (Reinhardt et al. 2022). <i>Populus nigra, the black poplar, is a species of cottonwood poplar, the species is native to Europe, southwest and central Asia, and northwest Africa</i>
Siberian Elm	<i>Ulmus pumila L.</i>	Perennial	Lignocelulose	Ornamental plant, biomass	MDF Boards, Graphene & Nanocarbons, Biochar	Siberian elm is native to Asia, widely distributed throughout China, Korea, Mongolia, East Russia and Central Asia. Siberian is adapted to all growing conditions, particularly its hardness, drought tolerance and adaptation to different environments. In Spain it grows naturalized in ditches, slopes and marginal lands. Siberian elm is an extremely hardy tree, deciduous, rapidly - growing to 25 m tall. It could be used to produce biomass in short rotation coppice
Melilotus	<i>Melilotus officinalis L.</i>	Biennial (in MIDAS to be grown like a winter-annual)	Lignocelulose	Biogas (and organic fertilizer from the digestate)	Particleboards	Melilot is a C3 legume that was first discovered for use in Germany in 2008 due to its high biomass yield, high nectar production and suitability for biogas production. In addition, melilot is a biennial plant native to Europe, so melilot as a whole has always received a lot of attention from farmers because it is a more environmentally sustainable biogas crop than silage maize. The area under melilot is still very small (no figures are available yet), but since 2019, incentives have been introduced in several states.
Guayule	<i>Parthenium argentatum A.Gray</i>	Perennial	Rubber, Latex	Guayule rubber, hypoallergenic latex; (wood preservatives, paints and adhesives from the resin)	Particleboards; Latex for gloves; Rubber for Tires; Resins for covering material for particleboards; Bagasse: MDF Boards Biochar	Guayule is a shrub, belonging to the Asteraceae family, originally growing in semi-arid regions in Mexico and the Southern USA; well suited to the semi-arid areas of Southern Europe; It is introduced as a biennial or multiannual crop for the production of rubber; irrigation needed 500-1300mm
Switchgrass	<i>Panicum virgatum L.</i>	Perennial	Lignocelulose	Forage, CHP, erosion mitigation, wildlife habitat	Biochar, Graphene & Nanocarbons	Erect and caespitose plant, 1-3 m tall. Associated to their latitudinal origin, cultivars of switchgrass can be placed into two distinct ecotypes: upland and lowland. Upland ecotypes are better adapted to the drier and colder habitats, while lowlands tend to thrive in warmer, wetter habitats.
Paulownia	<i>Paulownia tomentosa</i>	Perennial	Lignocelulose	Ornamental plant, firewood, fodder, wood boxes and clogs, dye, soundboards (e.g., guitar), skis, surfboard cores,	Particleboards, MDF Boards, Graphene & Nanocarbons, Biochar	Paulownia is a genus of seven to 17 species of hardwood tree (depending on taxonomic authority) in the family Paulowniaceae. Paulownia species are native to eastern and central Asia and can grow to maturity in under 10 years and produce strong, lightweight timber. Paulownia trees can grow over 30 metres tall and have large heart shaped leaves. Paulownia needs much light and does not like high water tables

White Mustard	<i>Brassica alba L. (Rabenh)</i>	Annual	Oil	oil for biodiesel/biolubricant, spice crop, fodder crop, organic fertilizer for sideration, remove toxic heavy metals from the soil (phytoremediation).	Biodegradable biolubricants, Agricultural Biostimulants, Biodegradable in soil mulch films; seed meal: adhesives for particleboards	Annual industrial oil crop that belongs to the Brassicaceae and has its origin in the Mediterranean. It can grow on different types of soil and tolerates extreme weather conditions well. Additionally it has a good tolerance against many diseases and harmful insects. The largest mass of roots is found in a layer 25–30 cm deep. The height ranges from 1–1.8 m (in Serbia). The weight of 1000 seeds is 4–7 g. The seeds contain 30% oil, 25% protein, mucilage, myrosinase enzyme, sinapin, sinapic acid, and about 2.5% sinalbin glycoside (sinalboside). The seeds are rich in calcium, magnesium, potassium, and vitamins, as well as 4-hydroxybenzyl glucosinolate. Mucilage is a valuable bioproduct used for emulsification, water retention, and stabilization. The seed has a high content of phenolic compounds, which makes it a rich source of natural antioxidants. The seed oil is not recommended for human consumption due to the high content of erucic acid.
Lavender	<i>Lavandula angustifolia Miller,</i>	Perennial	Oil	Essential oil; perfumes, pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, personal care and home maintenance product	Bioherbicides	Small, non-hardy perennial evergreen shrub native to the Mediterranean, with a typical productive life of about 10 years. It can grow on coarse, rocky soils, and coastal climate. Long-living perennial crop that requires high temperatures for germination

5. Description innovative cropping systems (WP3)

The objective of MIDAS is to develop new innovative bio-based value chains and webs from sustainably produced biomass from marginal lands. One pillar of this approach is the biomass production in innovative cropping systems like agroforestry and intercropping (WP3). The following section describes the conceptual understanding of these innovative cropping systems (Figure 7).

Figure 7 Innovative cropping systems in MIDAS – Agroforestry and intercropping of perennial and annual crops

Agroforestry is a cropping and land-use system where woody perennials (trees, shrubs, etc.) are deliberately used on the same land management unit as agricultural crops and/or animals (Mosquera-Losada et al. op. 2009). The integration can be either in a spatial mixture or in temporal sequence.

Agroforestry can be considered at a range of scales: field-scale, farm-scale and landscape scale. This system can provide a multitude of economic, social, and environmental benefits like reduction of nutrients and pesticides, sequestration of carbon, increase of soil quality, improvement of wildlife habitats, control of erosion, reduction of fuel use, and higher resilience against future uncertainty of production (Wilson und Lovell 2016).

Intercropping is a cropping system that involves growing two or more crop species (i.e., crop mixture cropping) or genotypes (i.e., cultivar mixture cropping) in the same area and coexisting for a time so that they interact agronomically (John H. Vandermeer 1989; Brooker et al. 2015). It can be designed using different spatial, temporal, or functional arrangements (e.g., in row, strip, relay or push-pull schemes) (Burgess et al. 2022). There are different types of intercropping:

- Mixed cropping: sowing multiple crop species or cultivars in the same field at the same time, in a mixture with a given seeding ratio but random spatial arrangement.
- Row intercropping: sowing multiple crop species in the same field at the same time in alternate rows.
- Strip intercropping: sowing two (or more) crop species in the same field at the same time in multi-row strips wide enough to allow independent cultivation.

- Relay cropping: intercropping of two crop species in which the second species is under-sown in the first at a later point in the growing season.

In the MIDAS project a number of promising industrial crops have been selected (Table 4 & 5) to be tested in several case studies with different marginality conditions in Europe under real operational conditions (farm-scale) in different cropping systems. The case studies are aimed at collecting real productivity data to be used for value-chain analysis and integrated assessment in WP5. Thirteen partners (CIEMAT, CREA, CRES, CZECHEMP, European Carbon Farmers, GuaTecs, IFVC, ITAB, Novamont, Soltub, UHOH, UNIBO and UNICT) established large field trials using different crops and cropping systems (WP3). Figure 8 shows the location and environmental zones of these case studies.

Figure 8 Sites and environmental zones of the case studies in MIDAS

The following section describes the ongoing case studies in MIDAS. Information shown is based on data that has been generated with the data entry sheets, discussions with partners and presentations during joint meetings. As some case studies are not fully established yet (as of October 2023) due to various difficulties the following information is provisional and subject to change.

CIEMAT – Northern Spain

In light of task 3.2.1 and 3.2.2 CIEMAT is carrying out two field trials on selected perennial and annual crops. The crops and case study design are presented in table 6:

Table 6 CIEMAT - Case study with innovative cropping systems in MIDAS

Institution	Geographical Information		Marginality		Case study information				
	City	Region	Marginality classification (MAGIC)	Characteristics	Case study design	Size	No. Plots; plot size	Crop Name	Cycle
CIEMAT	Soria	Northern Spain	Adverse Climate (dryness); Low soil fertility	Rainfall ≈500 mm, Poor chemical properties: Sand >75%; Organic matter: ≈1%,	intercropping	0.50 ha	3 x 3 anual crop strips of 384 m2 each + 4 strips of 384 m2 with 3 rows of lavenders each	Lavender	Perennial
								Crambe	Annual
								Safflower	Annual
								Melilot	Annual
					agroforst	0.50 ha	3 x 3 anual crop strips of 384 m2 each + 4 strips of 384 m2 with 3 rows of elms each	Elm	Perennial
								Crambe	Annual
								Safflower	Annual
								Melilot	Annual

Figure 9 presents the case study location and plot design of the case study by CIEMAT. The size of the trial is 0.50 ha each. In the two trials four strips of perennial crops (lavender or elm) with three rows each are tested with 3 strips of annual crops (Crambe; Safflower, Melilot).

Figure 9 CIEMAT - Case study location and plot design

Figure 10 shows the established crops end of June 2023.

Figure 10 CIEMAT – Case study with Crambe, Melilot and Safflower, Pictures were taken on the 28th June 2023

CREA – Italy

In light of task 3.2.2 CREA is carrying out an agroforestry field trial on selected perennial and annual crops. The crops and case study design are presented in table 7:

Table 7 CREA - Case study with innovative cropping systems in MIDAS

Institution	Geographical Information		Marginality		Case study information				
	City	Region	Marginality classification (MAGIC)	Characteristics	Case study design	Size	No. Plots; plot size	Crop Name	Cycle
Crea	Monterotondo (Rome)	Italy	Excessive wetness	Flooding, very limited soil drainage	agroforest	0.6 ha	1 plot; 50x120m; 6x1m plant spacing	Poplar	Perennial
				Delay of sowing and germination, low productivity				Crambe	Annual
				Safflower				Annual	

Figure 11 presents the plot design of the case study by CREA. The size of the trial is .60 ha. The area is characterized by a strong marginality due to frequent flooding. The field is formed by the intercropping of poplars with safflower and crambe placed in the interrow.

Figure 11 CREA - Case study plot design

Figure 12 shows the field and the established crops.

Figure 12 CREA – Case study with Poplar, Crambe and Safflower

CRES – Western Greece

In light of task 3.2.1 CRES is carrying out two intercropping field trials on selected perennial and annual crops. The crops and case study design are presented in table 8:

Table 8 CRES – Intercropping case study with innovative cropping systems in MIDAS

Institution	Geographical Information		Marginality		Case study information				
	City	Region	Marginality classification (MAGIC)	Characteristics	Case study design	Size	No. Plots; plot size	Crop Name	Cycle
CRES	Lexaina/Ilia	Western Greece	Unfavorable soil texture, Low fertility of soil	poor drainage, low organic matter, sandy soil	intercropping	0.3 ha	-	Miscanthus	Perennial
								Castor	Annual
								Safflower	Annual
								Sorghum	Annual
	Vonitsa	Western Greece	Steep slope	Slope (>12%), poor drainage during winter/spring	intercropping	0.3 ha	-	Switchgrass	Perennial
								Castor	Annual
Safflower	Annual								
Sorghum	Annual								

Figure 13 presents the case study location and plot designs of the two intercropping case study by CRES. The size of the trial is 0.30 ha each. In the two trials four strips of perennial crops (Miscanthus or Switchgrass) with three rows each are tested with 3 strips of annual crops (Castor; Safflower, Sorghum).

Figure 13 CRES - Case study location and plot design

CRES – Central Greece

In light of task 3.2.2 CRES is carrying out two agroforestry field trial on selected perennial and annual crops. The crops and case study design are presented in table 9:

Table 9 CRES - Agroforestry case study with innovative cropping systems in MIDAS

Institution	Geographical Information		Marginality		Case study information				
	City	Region	Marginality classification (MAGIC)	Characteristics	Case study design	Size	No. Plots; plot size	Crop Name	Cycle
CRES	Neo Gonia Chalkidikis	Greece	Low fertility of soil	poor texture, low organic matter	agroforest	0,3 ha	-	Lavender	Perennial
								Castor	Annual
								Safflower	Annual
								Crambe	Annual
	Krini Chalkidikis	Greece	Unfavorable soil texture, Low fertility of soil,	poor texture, low organic matter	intercropping	0,3 ha	-	Poplar	Perennial
								Castor	Annual
							Safflower	Annual	
							Crambe	Annual	

Figure 14 presents the case study location and plot designs of the two agroforestry case study by CRES. The size of the trial is 0,30 ha each. In the two trials four strips of perennial crops (Poplar or Lavender) with three rows each are tested with 3 strips of annual crops (Castor; Safflower, Hemp).

CzechHemp – Northern Czech Republic

In light of task 3.2.1 CzechHemp is carrying out a intercropping field trial on selected perennial and annual crops. The crops and case study design are presented in table 10:

Table 10 CzechHemp - Case study with innovative cropping systems in MIDAS

Institution	Geographical Information		Marginality		Case study information				
	City	Region	Marginality classification (MAGIC)	Characteristics	Case study design	Size	No. Plots; plot size	Crop Name	Cycle
CzechHemp	Ahníkov	Chomutov, Czech Republic	Adverse chemical composition of soil. Low fertility of soil.	Poor agrochemical properties, low organic matter	Intercropping	0,504 ha	1 plot	Miscanthus	Perennial
								Sorghum	Annual
								Hemp	Annual
								Safflower	Annual

Figure 15 presents the case study location and plot design of the case study by CzechHemp. The size of the trial is 0,504 ha. In the trial strips of perennial crops (Miscanthus) are tested with strips of annual crops (Sorghum, Hemp, Safflower).

Figure 15 CzechHemp - Case study location and plot design

Figure 16 shows the field.

Figure 16 CzechHemp – Case study with Miscanthus, Hemp, Safflower and Sorghum

European Carbon Farmers – Northern Poland

In light of task 3.2.2 European Carbon Farmers is carrying out an agroforestry field trial on selected perennial and annual crops. The crops and case study design are presented in table 11:

Table 11 European Carbon Farmers - Case study with innovative cropping systems in MIDAS

Institution	Geographical Information		Marginality		Case study information				
	City	Region	Marginality classification (MAGIC)	Characteristics	Case study design	Size	No. Plots; plot size	Crop Name	Cycle
European Carbon Farmers	Świerznica, Stegna Municipality	Northern Poland	Adverse chemical composition of soil	sandy and dry soil (crops drying out during the production period)	agroforst	0,5538 ha	1 plot	(Black) Poplar	Perennial
			Low fertility of soil					Dactylis	-
				<i>Meadow Fescue</i>				-	
				<i>Bromus</i>				-	

Figure 17 presents the case study location and plot design of the case study by European Carbon Farmers. The size of the trial is 0,554 ha. The case study aims to combine the highest-quality hay production on marginal land with poplar production. The case study was developed as a response to harsh natural environmental conditions present in the demo site location (very poor soils), which result in the farm not being able to harvest any meaningful production from the plot of land.

Figure 17 European Carbon Farmers - Case study location and plot design

Figure 18 European Carbon Farmers – Case study with Poplar and different grasses

Figure 18 shows the field and the established crops.

GuaTecs – Southern France

In light of task 3.2.1 GuaTecs in cooperation with Valorhiz is carrying out an intercropping field trial on selected perennial and annual crops. The crops and case study design are presented in table 12:

Table 12 GuaTecs - Case study with innovative cropping systems in MIDAS

Institution	Geographical Information		Marginality		Case study information				
	City	Region	Marginality classification (MAGIC)	Characteristics	Case study design	Size	No. Plots; plot size	Crop Name	Cycle
GuaTecs	Montpellier	Southern France, (Occitanie Department Gard)	Unfavorable soil texture and stoniness, shallow rooting depth, Adverse chemical composition of soil	poor chemical properties, Heavy soil along the profile: clay % > 30, Very low Phosphorus availability: High pH: very alkaline soil Very low Organic Matter Content, Dryness: water use restrictions in the area	intercropping	2500m ²	not specified yet	Guayule	Perennial
								Hemp	Annual
								Safflower	Annual

Figure 19 presents the case study plot of the case study by GuaTecs. In the trial strips of perennial crops (Guayule) are tested with strips of annual crops (Safflower, Hemp). So far only Guayule has been planted.

Figure 19 GuaTecs - Case study location

Figure 20 shows the Guayule plant and its various components.

Figure 20 Parts of the Guayule plant (Rousset et al. 2021)

IFVC – Northern Serbia

In light of task 3.2.1 IFVC is carrying out an intercropping field trial on selected perennial and annual crops. The crops and case study design are presented in table 13:

Table 13 IFVC - Case study with innovative cropping systems in MIDAS

Institution	Geographical Information		Marginality		Case study information				
	City	Region	Marginality classification (MAGIC)	Characteristics	Case study design	Size	No. Plots; plot size	Crop Name	Cycle
IFVC	Žabalj	Northern Serbia	Excessive wetness, low soil fertility, unfavorable chemical conditions, Limitations in rooting; adverse terrain	Limited soil drainage or excess soil moisture, low content of organic matter in the soil and possibly acidity or alkalinity, salinity, high clay content, risks of flooding	intercropping perennial x annual	24092 m	0.66 ha; 3 plots: perennial 45 x 4 m, annual 45 x10 m, plant spacing depend on the species	Miscanthus	Perennial
								Safflower	Annual
								White Mustard	Annual
								Sorghum	Annual
								Crambe	Annual

Figure 21 presents the case study location and plot design of the case study by IFVC. The size of the trial is 0.66 ha. The case study includes the perennial crop miscanthus, which remains during the field trial in the same place on the plot, and 3 annual species: safflower, Brassica (white mustard in 2023, crambe in 2024-26), sorghum that alternate in the field.

Figure 21 IFVC- Case study location and plot design

ITAP – Central Spain

In light of task 3.2.1 ITAP is carrying out an intercropping field trial on selected perennial and annual crops. The crops and case study design are presented in table 14:

Table 14 ITAP - Case study with innovative cropping systems in MIDAS

Institution	Geographical Information		Marginality		Case study information				
	City	Region	Marginality classification (MAGIC)	Characteristics	Case study design	Size	No. Plots; plot size	Crop Name	Cycle
ITAP	Fuentidueña de Tajo (Madrid).	Central Spain	Low fertility of soil, Adverse climate (dryness).	Organic matter: < 2%; Soil texture: sand (>70%); Moderate soil depth;	Intercropping	0.5025 ha	1 plot; 67m length; 6m(A) and 3m(P) strips; 4 lines; 7344 plants.	Guayule	Perennial
								Safflower	Annual
								Hemp	Annual

Figure 22 presents the case study location and plot design of the case study by ITAP. The size of the trial is 0.5025 ha. In this case study Guayule as a perennial crop is tested with Hemp and Safflower in an intercropping scheme to determine if guayule mulching has advantages over traditional guayule management.

Figure 22 ITAP- Case study location and plot design

Figure 23 shows the field and the partly established crops.

Figure 23 ITAP - Case study with Guayule, Safflower and Hemp

Novamont – Italy

In light of task 3.2.1 Novamont is carrying out two intercropping field trials on selected perennial and annual crops. The crops and case study design are presented in table 15:

Table 15 Novamont - Case study with innovative cropping systems in MIDAS

Institution	Geographical Information		Marginality		Case study information				
	City	Region	Marginality classification (MAGIC)	Characteristics	Case study design	Size	No. Plots; plot size	Crop Name	Cycle
Novamont	Fiumicino (Rome)	Central Italy	Adverse temperature, Low fertility of soil	Soil characteristics, Loam (<50%), alkaline (8.0)	intercropping	1ha	4 plots	Cardoon	Perennial
								Safflower	Annual
								Castor	Annual

Figure 24 presents the case study locations and plot designs of the case studies by Novamont. The size of the trials is 1 ha. In this case studies strip-intercropping between cardoon as perianial crop and safflower or castor as annual crops is tested.

Figure 24 Novamont - Case study location and plot design

Soltub – Central Hungary

In light of task 3.2.1 and task 3.2.2 Soltub is carrying out two field trials on selected perennial and annual crops. The crops and case study design are presented in table 16:

Table 16 Soltub - Case study with innovative cropping systems in MIDAS

Institution	Geographical Information		Marginality		Case study information				
	City	Region	Marginality classification (MAGIC)	Characteristics	Case study design	Size	No. Plots; plot size	Crop Name	Cycle
Soltub	Gödöllő	Central Hungary	Adverse climate (dryness), adverse chemical composition as heterogenic soil, adverse terrain conditions	(30 ha plot): 5-10 % slope, in case of heavy rainfalls erosion occurs, brown forest soil in upper A and B layers with sandy spots, in the heterogenic soil stone spots can occur. The plots under cultivation and is fence protected.	intercropping	0.5 ha	4 blocks in random repetition, (1 intercropping, 1 agroforst, 2x combined)	Miscanthus Hemp Carinata Sorghum	Perennial Annual Annual Annual
					agroforst			Poplar Hemp Carinata Sorghum	Perennial Annual Annual Annual

Figure 25 presents the case study location and plot design of the case study by Soltub. The size of the trial is 0.5 ha each. In the two trials strips of perennial crops (Miscanthus and Poplar) are tested in random repetition (4 blocks) with strips of annual crops (Hemp, Carinata, Sorghum).

Figure 25 Soltub - Case study plot design

UHOH – Southern Germany

In light of task 3.2.1 UHOH is carrying out an intercropping field trial on selected perennial and annual crops. The crops and case study design are presented in table 17:

Table 17 UHOH - Case study with innovative cropping systems in MIDAS

Institution	Geographical Information		Marginality		Case study information				
	City	Region	Marginality classification (MAGIC)	Characteristics	Case study design	Size	No. Plots; plot size	Crop Name	Cycle
UHOH	Eningen unter Achalm	Southern Germany	Limitations in rooting	Shallow, stoney soil (JRC thresholds)	Intercrop- ping	0.53 ha	4 plots; 12x30m	Miscanthus	Perennial
								Hemp	Annual
								Melilotus	Annual
								Crambe	Annual

Figure 26 presents the case study location and plot design of the case study by UHOH. The size of the trial is 0,53 ha.

Figure 26 UHOH case study location and plot design - Location of the MIDAS field trial of the University of Hohenheim (UHOH, coordinates: 48°28'15.7"N 9°18'06.2"E) shown by satellite images from 200 km and 20 km.

Figure 28 UHOH case study - established crops (Crambe, Hemp, Miscanthus)

Figure 27 UHOH case study - drone picture (40m altitude).

UNIBO – Italy

In light of task 3.2.1 UNIBO is carrying out an intercropping field trial on selected perennial and annual crops. The crops and case study design are presented in table 18:

Table 18 UNIBO - Case study with innovative cropping systems in MIDAS

Institution	Geographical Information		Marginality		Case study information				
	City	Region	Marginality classification (MAGIC)	Characteristics	Case study design	Size	No. Plots; plot size	Crop Name	Cycle
UNIBO	Bo-logna	Northern - central Italy	Adverse terrain, Limitations in rooting (a. Unfavourable soil texture	Steep Slope (>12%), very sandy soil (organic farm) >70% sand	intercropping	1 ha	12 plots in 3 blocks, size of individual plot about 800 m ²	Miscanthus	Perennial
								Hemp	Annual
								Safflower	Annual
								Crambe	Annual

Figure 29 presents the case plot design of the case study by UNIBO. The size of the trial is 1 ha. The case study is located on a fallow land with variable slopes from 10 to 20% and a very sandy soil (about 75% in some points of the field). The farm is organic, and it's also included in a national park (Parco dei Gessi).

Figure 29 UNIBO- Case study plot design

Figure 30 shows the field and the established crops.

Figure 30 UNIBO - Case study with Miscanthus, Hemp, Safflower and Crambe

UNICT – Southern Italy

In light of task 3.2.1 UNICT is carrying out an intercropping field trial on selected perennial and annual crops. The crops and case study design are presented in table 19:

Table 19 UNICT - Case study with innovative cropping systems in MIDAS

Institution	Geographical Information		Marginality		Case study information				
	City	Region	Marginality classification (MAGIC)	Characteristics	Case study design	Size	No. Plots; plot size	Crop Name	Cycle
UNICT	Catania	Sicily, Southern Italy	Adverse chemical composition of soil; adverse climate, steep slope	Slope 15%; Low soil organic matter <1%; precipitation/potential evapotranspiration < 0.5	intercropping	0.468 ha	6x6m strips	Cardoon	Perennial
								Hemp	Annual
								Safflower	Annual
								Castor	Annual

Figure 31 presents the case study location and plot design of the case study by UNICT. The size of the trial is 0.468 ha. In this case study alley cropping of perennial cardoon intercropped with annual crops in rotation is tested. The annual crops are rainfed (hemp and safflower) or irrigated (castor)

Figure 31 UNICT - Case study location and plot design

6. Innovative bio-based products (WP4)

Producing biomass is the initial step of the value generation process in a bioeconomy. Many other stakeholders are involved in using and valorizing bio-based resources. The development of innovative bio-based products and applications therefore is an important pillar for the development of innovative new value chains and webs.

As previously stated the objective of MIDAS is to develop new innovative bio-based value chains and webs from sustainably produced biomass from marginal lands. In addition to pillar one, the biomass production previously described in chapter 5, the development of innovative bio-based products and applications is another important pillar for the development of innovative new value chains and webs for the European Bioeconomy.

The different types of low ILUC feedstock (Chapter 4) will be transformed into 12 different products through various conversion technologies (WP4). Lignocellulosic crops with their special characteristics (e.g, fibers) are directly tested for the manufacture of biomaterials (Task 4.2). Compounds of interest are extracted from oilcrops and speciality crops (Task 4.1) before the bagasse resulting from the process is used following the concept of the circular use of biomass (Task 4.2).

The following section describes the innovative bio-based products that are being developed in MIDAS. Information shown is based on data that has been generated with the data entry sheets, discussions with partners and presentations during joint meetings.

6.1 Innovative bio-based products from oilseed crops

1. Biodegradable biolubricants for agricultural machinery - Novamont

Raw Material	Supplied by
Oil seeds – Vegetable Oil	Different MIDAS partners

New biodegradable biolubricants will be formulated from vegetable oils extracted from seeds. Particular attention will be paid to the selection of the additives, which must guarantee biodegradability and non-toxicity. The most promising bio lubricant formulations will be characterised by HELLE-NiQ ENERGY for their physico-chemical and tribological properties and evaluated against OEM test methods normally used for lubricants of the UTTO category.

UTTO (Universal Tractor Transmission Oil): is a fluid for hydraulic systems that operates at the same time for differential lubrication, gear boxes and hydrodynamic brakes in tractors and, more generally, in all earthmoving machinery used especially in agriculture.

An extensive work in formulation improvements is needed, starting from "**ashless**" additives with good environmental profile, free of mineral oil and based on vegetable oil and biodegradable synthetic esters that confer a high oxidation stability even in conditions of continuous stress.

The aim is to create a product **with higher viscosity index and high extreme pressure performance**. Biodegradable UTTO are a very promising technology. Due to their plant origin and given their **rapid biodegradability**, bio-lubricants are a **viable alternative to fossil-derived products**, offering environmentally sustainable solutions to **minimize the risks associated with the dispersion of such products into the ecosystem**.

2. Agricultural biostimulants for on-crop use – Novamont

Raw Material	Supplied by
Seed cake	Different MIDAS partners

An innovative protocol will be defined for the obtainment of protein hydrolysates from the seed cake left after by oil extraction performed by NOVAMONT towards use in new formulations of low impact biostimulants for application at various crops. The seed meal will be treated through enzymatic hydrolysis (protease) optimizing enzyme dosage, temperature, pH, mixing conditions, reaction time, etc., towards the maximization of the different compounds (polypeptides) with a biostimulant effect. The hydrolysate will be further concentrated to achieve the desired concentration of the targeted compounds.

- Cardoon and safflower seeds are pressed to extract vegetable oil (Task 4.1.1; 4.1.3; 4.1.7) and **seed cake** (Task 4.1.2).
- The oil cake **contains valuable proteins and active ingredients** for the obtainment of protein hydrolysates.

3. Biodegradable in soil mulch films for use in agricultural trials – Novamont

Raw Material	Supplied by
Oil seeds – Vegetable oil	Different MIDAS partners
Biochar (20 µm)	RE-CORD

Vegetable oils from selected oil crops will be converted by NOVAMONT, through proprietary chemical and biotechnological processes, into purified monomers that will be used in polymerization and reactive extrusion processes in order to obtain biodegradable and compostable biomaterials suitable to be transformed through film-blowing into biodegradable in soil mulch films.

Moreover, biochar from RE-CORD will be tested and valorised as a biobased substitute of Carbon Black masterbatch (black dye) to enhance renewability content of mulch film.

- **Three different types of film developed for different needs:**
 - Standard material for horticultural spring summer cycles;
 - long term performance material;
 - High content of renewable biomaterials suitable also for organic farming;
- **Main characteristics of mulch film**
 - **Available color:** black, white / black, green, grey (with based biodegradable master)
 - **Standard thickness:** 15 microns; innovative films starting from 10 microns or long-standing films up to 40 microns.
 - **Average shelf life:** from 2 to 10 months modulating the thickness.
 - Crops: Suitable for industrial crops (lettuce, melon, strawberry, zucchini, grapevine, rice, tomato, asparagus).

6.2 Innovative bio-based products from speciality crops

4. Protein modified phenol-formaldehyde resins for plywood panels - CHIMAR

Raw Material	Supplied by
Proteins	Novamont and different MIDAS partners
Soy flour	VALBOPAN

CHIMAR will develop phenol-formaldehyde type adhesives for particleboards by replacing part of phenol by proteins extracted from seed cake left behind by oil extraction and by protein from

specialty crops. The replacement will start from low levels and the target is a 100% substitution. The level of substitution will start at low levels (eg 20%) and escalate by 10% with the goal of 100% phenol replacement. All **successful resins will be characterized for their properties by typical laboratory analysis** (eg solids, pH, gel time, water tolerance, etc.). The bonding ability of the successful resins will be tested through their application in the production of plywood panels on a laboratory/pilot scale. The properties of the successful panels will be tested according to European standards EN314.1 and EN 414.2

5. Adhesives and coatings as covering material for particleboards – CHIMAR

Raw Material	Supplied by
Guayule resin	UCLM

CHIMAR will produce covering materials with **water repellence properties** for particleboards by using guayule resins. CHIMAR will experiment with various methods of applying the material and successful applications will be tested for resistance to water. UCLM will carry out the large-scale extraction of the resins (500 L batch) after the corresponding optimization at large lab scale extractions (5-25 kg) to select the solvent and the operating conditions. When the guayule resin from large-scale production becomes available, CHIMAR will receive a sample of it - about 5kg) and evaluate it as covering material of particleboards following the most successful application process depending on the results of the previous work

5.1 Latex covered wood-based panels – CHIMAR

Raw Material	Supplied by
Hevea latex	GUATECS
Guayule latex	GUATECS

CHIMAR will use **latex as a covering material** of wood-based panels (particleboards, MDF, etc) to produce panels with a new surface.

6. Guayulue Latex for gloves and wood panel coverings – GuaTecs; CHIMAR

Raw Material	Supplied by
Guayule	GUATECS

GuaTecs will improve process efficiency of a current pilot-plant infrastructure for extracting unique **allergy-free latex** from guayule cultivated, paying attention to achieve the reproducibility of product quality (especially latex stability, film properties) via process adjustment. Large scale samples will be provided for **evaluation of gloves manufactured under industrial conditions** (by Piercan a first-ranked European manufacturer). In addition, GUATECS will supply latex to CHIMAR for testing it as covering material for wood-based panels (eg particleboards, MDF, etc). Guayule latex, like hevea latex, is a dispersion of polyisoprene in water. This **polyisoprene** has a very low vitreous transition temperature, thus it is a rubber at ambient temperature. It is not comparable to the Styrene Butadiene or Styrene Acrylate synthetic latexes used in paint or paper applications, having a higher vitreous temperature, that behaves like rigid plastic at ambient temperature.

Bagasse will be used in the wood-panel production by CHIMAR (9.)

7. Guayule Rubber for Tires – Nokian Tyres

Material	Supplied by
Natural rubber from guayule latex	UCLM
Natural rubber from guayule biomass	UCLM

In a sequential extraction process, guayule will be extracted with the purpose of obtaining **rubber for the manufacturing of tires**. During the project guayule rubber properties and the extraction process will be evaluated with UCML (using gram-scale samples). As in the case of resins, UCLM will optimize the rubber extraction conditions for large-scale extraction (500 L batch), selecting the most suitable solvents. Manufactured tyres by NOKIAN will be tested under real life conditions. Based on the feedback from NOKIAN laboratory compound recipe development, the **sequential extraction process** will be optimized. In rubber compound similar or better properties than hevea natural rubber compounds will be expected. At factory scale testing similar or better properties than in reference tires is expected when NR (Hevea) will be replaced partly or totally in compound. Also compound process behavior at factory scale will be evaluated. Critical properties are for example process behavior in rubber mixing and component raw adhesion.

6.3 Innovative bio-based products from oilcrops and speciality crops

8. Bioherbicides for use in agricultural trials – Novamont & CIEMAT

Material	Supplied by
Essential oils	CIEMAT
Pelargonic acid	NOVAMONT

Novel biodegradable in soil bio herbicides formulations based on bio-based pelargonic acid derived from the vegetable oils and the essential oils produced by CIEMAT will be developed and characterised by NOVAMONT. Tank mix and ready-mix new environmentally friendly adjuvants will be tested to define the optimal formulation strategy in order to achieve the same bioherbicide effects with a reduced bioherbicide dosage. Bio-based molecules providing synergic bioherbicide effects in combination with pelargonic acid will be also tested. Based on the in-use tests, the new bi-herbicide formulations will be refined/optimized in their biological performance and applied in WP2 fields. **Pelargonic acid is an efficient burndown weed control active ingredient, which acts by contact on the leaf surface**, resulting in rapid tissue desiccation. Results are usually visible within minutes after treatment. In MIDAS we will work on emulsion stabilization, in order to guarantee an efficient product distribution to increase product efficiency in order to reduce active ingredient content

6.4 Innovative bio-based products from lignocellulosic biomass and bagasse

9. Particleboards with residual lignocellulosic biomass - CHIMAR

Material	Supplied by
Hemp core	CRES
Siberian Elm	CIEMAT
Guayule bagasse	GUATECS
MIDAS biomass	CRES (hemp), NOVAMONT (cardoan), GUATECS (guayule) OTHER

CHIMAR will manufacture particleboards for various purposes (furniture, objects, wall finishes etc) by using MIDAS biomass (annual and perennial crops as well as woody species). MIDAS biomass will be used to **replace wood in the production of particleboards**. The replacement will start from low levels (e.g. 20-30%) and it will be gradually increased. The target is a 100% replacement of wood. CHIMAR will receive MIDAS biomass (delivered to CHIMAR in the form of chips and with a moisture content of less than 15%) for testing as wood substitute in the production of particleboards. Various substitution levels (at least 3) will be tested with the target of 100% sub-stitution. The panels production will be based on the typical process for the production of particleboards. Changes/modifications will be made to adjust the process to the special needs of MIDAS biomass.

10. MDF Boards with mixture from Guayule bagasse for different applications – Valbopan

Material	Supplied by
Guayule Bagasse	GUATECS
Siberian Elm	CIEMAT
Woody biomass	CRES
Protein modified phenol-formaldehyde resins	CHIMAR

Valbopan will produce coloured medium density fiberboards (MDF). Different feedstocks will be tested, **woody biomass** (poplar, Siberian elm) as well as **bagasse from speciality crops** (guayule), **together with natural resins**, to establish whether, alone or in combination, they could offer any improvement to the physicochemical features of the products they currently produce. In further steps MDF Boards with new adhesives and different particles will be tested. Test with wood fibers changing press temperature; addition of hardener; addition of adhesive.

11. Production of carbon nanofilaments (CNF) from waste streams and use as polymers additives in resins - UDS

Material	Supplied by
Biomass residues	
Lignocellulosic biomass	
Guayule	

UDS will produce bio-carbon nanofilaments and graphene (Bio-CNF&G) by using a kg-lab scale process unit based on two **novel thermo-catalytic reactor technologies**: an autothermal pyrolyzer/gasifier (ATP/G) and a CNF production catalytic reactor combining a fluid and a mobile bed inside the same vessel. The performance of the whole process will be evaluated based on the yield of the carbon production, and the quality of the bio-CNF. Finally, the handling of the produced Bio-CNF will be done in accordance with the prevailing laboratory and industrial norms.

12. Biochar and wood vinegar as soil improver and for seed priming – RE-CORD

Material	Supplied by
Guayule bagasse	GUATECS
Woody biomass (chips)	

RE-CORD will produce biochar and wood vinegar to assess its potential agronomic application as soil improver. Biochar from the woody biomass selected at lab and pilot scale will be produced by a **carbonization demo plant** (slow pyrolysis, rotary kiln, 100 kg/h of input biomass, continuous). The

Biochar produced will be **tested in the operational environment of the agronomic field trials**, also mixed with mature compost. The aqueous fraction of condensates, a byproduct commonly called wood-vinegar, will be separated from the oil fraction, characterized and tested on field to assess its potential use as bio stimulant (pre-sowing seed primer). The biochar produced will be characterized and its compliance with EU standards and regulations will be checked.

7. Superstructure – potential biomass to product pathways

The objective of MIDAS is to develop new innovative bio-based value chains and webs from sustainably produced biomass from marginal lands. Each of the crops listed in table 4 that are produced in the case studys (chapter 5) can be used for a multitude of products and applications (chapter 6). As described in chapter 2 we have applied a superstructure approach to map all potential biomass-to-product pathways resulting from this. The superstructure is a flowsheet that shows all the process alternatives for a given feedstock (Elyasi et al. 2021; Gu et al. 2022; Del Álvarez Castillo-Romo et al. 2018). With this approach we are able to show the **technological potential** for every industrial crop tested in MIDAS. For this Deliverable we therefore build superstructure(s) for the different feedstock categories based on the collected information to show the **technological potential of the industrial crops grown on marginal land**.

Figure 5 Colour code for the presentation of biomass-to-product pathways (superstructure)

Figure 5 shows the colour code that has been used to graphically represent the biomass-to-product pathways in superstructures. The crop category is presented in light blue, the feedstock (industrial crop) in turquoise, conversion processes in green, intermediates in grey and the end-products in red.

For MIDAS we identified 129 biomass-to-product pathways that are shown in the superstructures below. Because of the large number of identified pathways, we divided the supersturctures into two graphs per crop category.

Pathways orginiate from the case study regions, however in the following superstructures the different regions were not considered.

Oilcrops (1)

Figure 32 Identified biomass-to-product pathways - Superstructures Oilcrops (1)

Oilcrops (2)

Figure 33 Identified biomass-to-product pathways - Superstructures Oilcrops (2)

Lignocellulosic crops (1)

Figure 34 Identified biomass-to-product pathways - Superstructures lignocellulosic crops (1)

Lignocellulosic crops (2)

Figure 35 Identified biomass-to-product pathways - Superstructures lignocellulosic crops (2)

Speciality crops (1)

Figure 36 Identified biomass-to-product pathways - Superstructures speciality crops (1)

Speciality crops (2)

Figure 37 Identified biomass-to-product pathways - Superstructures speciality crops (2)

8. Outlook

Many different industrial crops, cropping systems and bio-based products are considered in the MIDAS project. Bringing together different regions, marginalities and stakeholders led to the identification of **129 biomass-to-product pathways** which were presented in a superstructure approach. With this approach we are able to show the **technological potential** for every industrial crop grown on marginal land in MIDAS. However, we could not say anything about the ecological, social or economic dimensions of these pathways.

In a next step we therefore use different criteria to identify promising biomass-to-product pathways for every case study from these superstructures. The identified biomass-to-product pathways will be assessed by means of the multi-criteria set, which includes quantitative and qualitative proxy indicators and incorporates context dependent factors at regional level, and by involving stakeholders. Depending on the context, criteria to be applied for the assessment include feasibility, viability and desirability aspects. We hereby want to identify the **regional implementation potential** of these pathways (Deliverable 5.2).

The goal of WP5 is to define value chain web concepts for different industrial crops based on the resulting selection of biomass-to-product pathways. Therefore, all biomass-to-product(s) pathways will be evaluated and the most promising will be selected for further assessment including LCSA in task 5.3 and modelling for biodiversity restoration potential (LARCH) in task 5.4. The information gathered throughout this workpackage will help to develop practical and policy recommendations and strategies for the implementation (task 5.5) based on LCSA, Biodiversity assessment and Stakeholder Involvement.

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The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101082070.

The consortium

